

CHEMISTRY

SYNTHESIS OF TRIMETHYLPHENOLS IN THE CATALYTIC ALKYLATION OF XYLENOL AND METHANOL AND APPLICATION IN THE PRODUCTION OF VITAMIN E (TOCOPHEROL)

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Abstract

In this article, the alkylation reactions of 2,6-, 2,5- and 2,3-dimethylphenols in the presence of methanol and CrCaY zeolite were investigated. The experiments were carried out at a temperature of 360°C and a volume flow rate of 0.82 st⁻¹. The results show that, regardless of the catalyst composition, the main conversion product of 2,6-dimethylphenol is 2,4,6-trimethylphenol. In the presence of CrCaY zeolite, 2,3,6-trimethylphenol is also formed with some selectivity. The potential application of trimethylphenols obtained in the alkylation process in the synthesis of tocopherol (vitamin E) is emphasized.

Keywords: 2,3,6 trimethylphenol, 2, 4, 6 trimethylphenol, xyleneol, methanol, methylphenol, cresol, vitamin E (tocopherol), application of trimethylphenols.

Introduction:

As a result of the conducted studies, it was found that 2,3,6-trimethylphenol was synthesized with 83% selectivity in the process of alkylation of 2,5-dimethylphenol with methanol, and 90.0% selectivity from the reaction of 2,3-dimethylphenol with methanol. The 2,3,5 trimethylphenol derivative synthesized from the reaction of 3,5 xyleneol with methanol was synthesized with 85.0% yield compared to the converted xyleneol, and in 4 cases from 2,4-dimethylphenol, in addition to the main isomer of trimethylphenol, hydroxyl and methyl groups react and other isomers are possible to form. It is also interesting to study the composition of the alkylates synthesized in the reaction of 2,6 and 3,4-dimethylphenols with methanol in the presence of Pd,H-mordenite. The yield of 2,6-dimethylphenol with a molar ratio of 1:1 from the reaction with methanol relative to xyleneol is assumed to be 94.5% [1].

The reaction of dimethylphenols with methanol was carried out by alkylation. A fixed bed catalyst was used for the reaction and the process was carried out in a stationary reactor. The process was carried out using PdCaY catalyst. Palladium was added to the zeolite in an amount of 0.6-3.1 mass % via an aqueous solution of [Pd(NH₃)₄]Cl₂. After that, it was annealed at 450°C for 2 hours in a dry air stream and kept in a hydrogen stream at 390°C. This process was continued for about 1 hour, and a Chrom-5 device was used for analysis[2].

When performing the alkylation reaction with methanol using 2,6- and 3,5-dimethylphenols, using ferrite catalysts and recording the results, certain results can be obtained. The process was carried out using a stationary mode reactor and analyzed with a Chrom-5 device. Zinc ferrite oxide system was used as a catalyst. The concentration of Zn oxide and Fe (III) oxide together in the ternary system was 27.0 wt% and Al oxide was used as a carrier. 2,3,4,6 tetramethylphenol and 2,4,6- and 2,3,6- trimethylphenols were obtained as the main products from the reaction of methanol with 2, 6-dimethylphenol. A number of different phenol derivatives are obtained from 3,5-dimethylphenol, which reacts with methanol, including: 2,3,5- trimethylphenol,

3,4,5- trimethylphenol, 2,3,4,5- tetramethylphenol and 2,3,5,6- tetramethylphenols [3].

Below we show the results of the synthesis of 2,6-dimethylphenol using 2-methylphenol together with phenol and methanol. NiCaY zeolite was used as a catalyst. The study was carried out in the temperature range of 325-385°C, and methanol was taken 2-4 times more than methanol. The volumetric flow rate of the liquid raw material when fed to the reactor was in the range of 0.7-1.1 st⁻¹. The following products were obtained from the alkylation reaction carried out with a nickel-containing faujasite catalyst: anisole, dimethyl ether, 2-methylphenol, 2,6-xyleneol, 2,4,6-trimethylphenol derivative, 4-methylphenol,. Although the composition of the alkylates obtained does not change depending on the reaction medium, the yield and selectivity vary. The main products obtained from the process are 2,6-dimethylphenol and 2-methylphenol. Another practically important property is that the molar ratio of 2,6-dimethylphenol to 2-methylphenol in the obtained alkylates is not 1÷0.6 : 1÷0.9 [4].

Conducting the research process

In this article, the essence of the main chemical reactions of 2,6-, 2,5- and 2,3-dimethylphenols in the presence of methanol and CrCaY zeolite was investigated. The experiments were carried out at a temperature of 360°C with a volume fraction of 0.82st⁻¹ and a molar ratio of dimethylphenol to methanol of 1:0.73÷1. From the analysis of the results given in Table 1, it can be seen that, regardless of the composition of the catalyst, the main transformation in the alkylation reaction of 2,6-dimethylphenol is the synthesis of 2,4,6 trimethylphenol by a sequential alkylation reaction. In the presence of chromium-containing CaY zeolite, the interaction of 2,6 dimethylphenol with methanol produces, along with 2,4,6-trimethylphenol, the 2,3,6-isomer with 11% selectivity, and the share of this isomer in the mixture with the 2,4,6-isomer is 3-6 times higher than in studies conducted with other catalysts. Also, in the presence of CrCaY zeolite, along with the 2,4,6 isomer, 2,4,5-trimethylphenol is synthesized in small amounts, to be precise, with a selectivity of 4%. It can

be concluded that the selectivity and yield of 2,4,6-trimethylphenol obtained from the reaction of 2,4-dimethylphenol with methanol are somewhat higher than those of the analogous trimethylphenol derivative obtained by the alkylation reaction of 2,6-xylenol with methanol. However, it is observed that the yield of the mixture of trimethylphenols formed from 2,4-dimethylphenol and methanol in the presence of CrCaY zeolite is somewhat lower compared to the case where 2,6-dimethylphenol is taken as the basis. Thus, the sequential conversion of 2,6- and 2,4-dimethylphenols synthesized from the reaction of 4-methylphenol and 2-methylphenol with methanol during the process results

in the formation of 2,4,6-trimethylphenol. The presence of other isomers, as well as 2,3,6- and 2,4,5-trimethylphenols in the alkylates, albeit in small amounts, indicates that isomerization or partial alkylation in the meta-state occurs. Looking at the results, it can be seen that in all cases, regardless of the catalyst and the structure of the xylenol used, the main product is 2,3,6-trimethylphenol. We concluded that even though the selectivity of the process for the 2,3,6-isomer synthesized with the participation of CrCaY zeolite is 2.5-3.5% higher than that of 2,3-dimethylphenol, the yield of the intended trimethylphenol is 3.0-3.9% lower.

Table 1.

Indicator name	Catalyst: CrCaY
Calculated yields for converted 2,6-dimethylphenol,%	
2,4,6-trimethylphenol	82.8
2,3,6-trimethylphenol	10.7
Yield of a mixture of 2,4,6- and 2,3,6-trimethylphenols calculated from the starting 2,6-dimethylphenol	41.9
Calculated yields for converted 2,4-dimethylphenol,%	
2,4,6-trimethylphenol	87.0
2,4,5-trimethylphenol	3.0
Yield of the mixture of trimethylphenols calculated from the starting 2,4-dimethylphenol	42.1

The molar ratio of the mixture of 2,5- and 2,3-dimethylphenols taken in equal proportions is 1:1. This was calculated based on methanol. In the case of 1:0.75, the material balances of the synthesized catalysts were calculated and determined, and the main and by-products of the process and their outputs were calculated based on the chemical composition of the acylate. For the first time, the 2,5- and 2,3-xylenols in the xylenol mixture were calculated and compared and are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Indicator name	Catalyst: CrCaY
	2,5-dimethylphenol-methanol
Yield of 2,3,6-trimethylphenol, calculated based on the reacted 2,5 dimethylphenol, %	85.5
The yield of 2,3,6-trimethylphenol, calculated from the starting 2,5-dimethylphenol,	35.5
	2,3-dimethylphenol-methanol
Yield of 2,3,6-trimethylphenol, calculated based on the reacted 2,3-dimethylphenol, %	82.0
Calculated based on starting 2,3-dimethylphenol	
Yield of 2,3,6-trimethylphenol, %	38.0

Use of 2,3,6 and 2, 4, 6-trimethylphenols in modern industries

Trimethylphenols are versatile organic compounds that are used in many sectors today and are expected to increase significantly in the future. However, taking into account the potential environmental and health effects of these trimethylphenols, the areas of use and the conditions of the production processes are always considered. Therefore, the development of more promising synthesis methods for methylphenols, including 2,4,6- and 2,3,6-trimethylphenols, which have become increasingly important recently, is a topical issue and is of particular interest to chemists. This is based on the alkylation reaction of dimethylphenols with methanol and the acquisition and use of catalysts with active, selective and high performance properties for this purpose can give impetus to a positive solution

to the issue. The importance of the use of trimethylphenols in pharmaceutical and other industries increases the need to acquire these substances. 2,3,6 and 2,4,6 derivatives of trimethylphenol can be used as intermediates in the production of drug molecules. Several isomers of trimethylphenol are actively used for the synthesis of vitamin E (tocopherol). They are also used in the production of pharmaceuticals in agriculture. 2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols can be used as model compounds in studies in the fields of organic chemistry and biochemistry.

2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols are used as intermediates in chemical processes. They are especially important in the production of resins, plastics and some pharmaceutical products. Phenol derivatives have antioxidant properties. Therefore, 2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols are used as oxidation inhibitors. Research

on trimethylphenols continues to reveal new and, in particular, more effective areas of use for these compounds. It is intended to expand the use of trimethylphenols on smaller scales and for more specific tasks, especially by combining them with nanotechnology.

2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols are important components for health in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. Some trimethylphenol derivatives are used for surface protection in the cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. Trimethylphenol derivatives can also be used as odorants and flavors in the cosmetics and food industries. They improve water quality by preventing the growth of microbes in water purification processes. 2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols, due to their strong antioxidant properties, prevent the deterioration of materials such as plastics, rubbers and oils by extending their life. They prevent oxidation in food products and extend the shelf life of products by preserving their freshness.

Result 1. For the first time in this study, we obtained trimethylphenols, which have many advantages for industry, using CrCaY catalyst, one of the selective zeolites. In the presence of CrCaY zeolite, methanol and 2,6-dimethylphenol were reacted at 360°C under conditions of volume fraction 0.82st⁻¹ and molar ratio of dimethylphenol to methanol 1:0.73÷1. After the process was completed, 2,3,6- and 2,4,6-trimethylphenol derivatives were synthesized. The properties of the obtained substance are shown in Table 1.

Conclusion 2. Consequently, the sequential conversion of 2,6- and 2,4-dimethylphenols synthesized from the reaction of 4-methylphenol and 2-methylphenol with methanol during the process leads to the formation of 2,4,6-trimethylphenol. The presence of other isomers in the alkylates, as well as the presence of 2,3,6- and 2,4,5-trimethylphenols, indicates that an isomerization or partial alkylation reaction occurs in the meta-state. The comparative results of the alkylation process of 2,3- and 2,5-dimethylphenols separately with methanol in the presence of CrCaY are shown above.

Result 3. 2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols are used as one of the most important raw materials in many industries in modern times, and the demand for these phenol derivatives is increasing day by day. These substances are used as intermediates in chemical processes. They

are especially important in the production of resins, plastics and some pharmaceutical products. Phenol derivatives have antioxidant properties. Isomers of trimethylphenol play a very important role in the synthesis of vitamin E (tocopherol). They are also widely used in the production of agricultural medicines. 2,3,6-2,4,6 trimethylphenols can be used as model compounds in studies in the fields of organic chemistry and biochemistry.

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